

Supplementary Information: SaGess: A Sampling Graph Denoising Diffusion Model for Scalable Graph Generation

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The supplementary information is organised as follows. First, Section 1 contains an ablation study regarding the number of subgraphs and the choice of k . In Section 2, the sampling schemes are discussed from a theoretical angle, focusing on the probability that the samples cover the whole graph. Section 3 gives the choices of hyperparameters. Section 4 details the computational resources used for this work.

1 Ablation Study

As mentioned in the paper, our model SAGESS is bound to train on a given set \mathcal{G} of N subgraphs. These subgraphs each have at most k nodes; for the induced subgraph sampling this number is exactly k , whereas the random walk samples and the snowball samples may contain fewer than k distinct nodes. In this section, we analyse how these hyperparameters, N and k , influence the results of SAGESS. For simplicity, we focus on the EuCore data set, although a similar experiment could be performed with each of the data sets in the main body.

1.1 Sample Impact on Generation

Ablation study setup First, to do so, we generate 10 synthetic networks trained on the EuCore data set. The goal here is to study the variation in performance for different setups of our framework, both on the size and the number of subgraphs generated. We show the results using the same set of statistics as used in the main body derived from a similar experiment, namely the graph statistics of Table 2 in Ref. [7], cluster coef. denoting the average local clustering coefficient, and CPL denoting the characteristic path length; we also report the number of nodes and the number of edges. Table 1 reports the results.

Global Structure As global structure indicators, we consider the number of nodes, the number of edges, maximum degree, assortativity, power law exponent, and characteristic shortest path length (CPL), keeping in mind that the algorithms aim to keep the number

of nodes and the number of edges relatively close to those of the observed graph. The SAGESS variants follow this pattern as well, as intended. Taking the standard deviations into account, we find that our SAGESS variants consistently produces graphs that have global structure which does not vary significantly from one sample to another; they have very small standard deviation. As an aside, in this experiment CELL is closest to the true graph regarding power law exponent and CPL, while DCSBM mimics assortativity best. Perhaps due to its local construction mechanism, SAGESS does not capture the global statistics as well as the other methods with these parameters on this data set.

Regarding the effect of the choice of N and k , increasing the number N of subgraphs from $10k$ to $40k$ gives a good improvement for the uniform sampling variant regarding the maximum degree, but does not affect the other variants much, taking the standard deviations into account. It gives a slight improvement in particular regarding the CPL. Reducing k from 40 to 20 leads to a deterioration for the snowball sampling variant (Ego) whereas it does not seem to strongly affect the random walk variant.

Local Structure On the other hand, local structures measured by number of triangles, number of squares, and average local clustering coefficient, do exhibit a certain amount of variation across each of our approaches, thus indicating a certain level of variability in the sampled graphs.

Considering the hyperparameters, we note that the above local structures appear to be impacted significantly by the sampling method, as well as N and k . This is evidenced by the fact that the bigger N , the more local substructures, such as triangles and squares, are obtained. It is also worth noting that having more data to train on does not necessarily imply better performance. This might be due to the fact that the denser substructures of the graph will be over-represented when we sample more subgraphs.

Moreover, we notice again that reducing the size of the subgraphs k helps on these local structures for the random walk sampling, whereas the opposite effect is observed for the snowball sampling. This observation can be further leveraged for improved performance, especially for the case of large-scale graphs to be generated, for

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Table 1: Mean values and standard deviation on different parameter setups of SAGESS on 10 different synthetic graphs produced on the EuCore data set. We show the results on the same set of statistics as in the main paper on different setups for the training data set we generate, for instance: $(40k, 40)$ means that we sampled 40,000 subgraphs of size 40 using a given sampling method.

Method	num nodes	num edges	num triangles	num squares	max deg	cluster coef.	assort.	power law exp	CPL
Real	1005	16,706	105,461	4,939,311	346	0.39935	-0.01099	1.3621	2.58693
SAGESS-Uni (10k, 40)	944 (± 6.73)	16,710 (± 4.49)	108,280 (± 1383)	5,760,499 ($\pm 122,614$)	278 (± 21.7)	0.3252 (± 0.0046)	-0.0691 (± 0.0097)	1.3530 (± 0.0027)	2.4773 (± 0.013)
SAGESS-Uni (40k, 40)	969 (± 4.01)	16,708 (± 1.11)	122,362 (± 859)	6,355,225 ($\pm 79,885$)	332 (± 12.6)	0.3971 (± 0.0061)	-0.0333 (± 0.0039)	1.3550 (± 0.0016)	2.5326 (± 0.0095)
SAGESS-RW (10k, 20)	914 (± 5.56)	16,709 (± 1.80)	130,923 (± 676)	6,986,290 ($\pm 80,666$)	381 (± 5.62)	0.4245 (± 0.0051)	-0.0385 (± 0.0020)	1.3513 (± 0.0028)	2.4909 (± 0.0077)
SAGESS-RW (10k, 40)	890 (± 9.36)	16,714 (± 5.11)	136,395 (± 1727)	7,924,207 ($\pm 167,462$)	350 (± 3.58)	0.4102 (± 0.0079)	-0.0385 (± 0.0042)	1.3469 (± 0.0028)	2.4725 (± 0.011)
SAGESS-RW (40k, 40)	914 (± 4.06)	16,712 (± 4.41)	140,486 (± 1501)	8,169,494 ($\pm 142,985$)	358 (± 6.42)	0.4199 (± 0.0059)	-0.0393 (± 0.0042)	1.3542 (± 0.0017)	2.5068 (± 0.0095)
SAGESS-Ego (10k, 20)	886 (± 4.32)	16,709 (± 1.47)	135,553 (± 1411)	7,766,822 (140,296)	354 ($\pm 16,1$)	0.4273 (± 0.0051)	-0.1066 (± 0.0067)	1.3483 (± 0.0018)	2.4437 (± 0.012)
SAGESS-Ego (10k, 40)	878 (± 5.88)	16,717 (± 6.07)	126,003 (± 1746)	7,024,802 ($\pm 187,183$)	356 (± 11.8)	0.3903 (± 0.0050)	-0.0560 (± 0.0073)	1.3407 (± 0.0022)	2.4443 (± 0.013)
SAGESS-Ego (40k, 40)	910 (± 5.67)	16,708 (± 1.81)	126,932 (± 847)	6,787,489 ($\pm 65,172$)	356 ($\pm 12,1$)	0.4240 (± 0.0056)	-0.0512 (± 0.0027)	1.3446 (± 0.0021)	2.4677 (± 0.0093)

which it is desirable to have a training set that contains smaller graphs in order to fit into memory, hence the preference to employ the random walk sampling. Finally, the fact that there is a certain amount of variation in our generated synthetic graphs implies that the model does not just yield the same graph again and again, which is reassuring for the end user and in line with the output expected from a synthetic data generation mechanism.

1.2 Graph Coverage Exploration

Additionally we explore the ability of uniform and random walk sampling strategies to provide a good coverage of the graph. To be precise we evaluate using the percentage of edges of the original graph that are captured in at least one of the sampled subgraphs. Indeed, if we undersample the original graph, our samples will not represent the distribution. However, we also do not wish to over sample too heavily as this will be computationally expensive when we are training the resultant model.

To make our comparison we will use the SBM model using 4 groups of size 400 with an internal connection probability of 0.2 and an external connection probability of 0.01. We use this model as we can create as many samples as we need to explore how the variability in network structure may affect the resultant coverage. To do so, we will sample 10 networks for each parameter value and plot the variation in coverage using a boxplot. It should also be noted that the results in this section may not generalise to other graphs, with different density or structural properties.

For the uniform model, there are two parameters, first the number of nodes that we sample for each subgraph, and second, the number of subgraphs we sample. For simplicity, we will vary each of the parameters separately and fix the other value to the value used in the paper, namely 10000 samples and a subgraph of size 30. The results of this model can be seen in Figure 1. We observe that the number of samples is an important parameter, requiring around 5000 samples to obtain at least 80% coverage, with 10000 samples having around 96% of the edges. However, the subgraph size parameter is far more influential, with a subgraph size below 20 resulting in less than 80% of the edges being captured. This is likely because the

Figure 1: Ablation on the uniform sampling model. Percentage of edges of the original graph that are part of any of the sampled subgraphs, as a function of the number of subgraph samples in the uniform node sampling model. **Top panel:** varies the number of subgraphs, with the size of subgraphs fixed at 30. **Bottom panel:** varies the subgraph size, with the number of subgraphs fixed at 10000.

number of possible connections scales like the square of the subgraph size. Thus, highlighting the tradeoff between the subgraph size and number of subgraphs with the consequent increase in computational complexity when training the model.

For the random walk model, similar to the uniform model there are again two parameters: the length of the random walk – similar to the subgraph size in the uniform sampling case, and the number of random walks per node – similar to the number of subgraphs sampled in the uniform case. Again, as in the uniform case, we vary each of the parameters separately and fix the other parameter to the value in the paper, namely 10 random walks per node and a random walk size of 30. The results can be seen in Figure 2. We first note that the results do not seem to be particularly sensitive to the number of subgraphs per node, with more than 4 subgraphs per node sufficient to give a very high coverage rate; this is not surprising as the number of subgraphs per node were chosen conservatively. The random walk length results demonstrate a similar behaviour to the similar subgraph size parameter, although it should be noted that as the random walk can go back on itself the parameter is the largest possible subgraph size. The results show that a relatively small length (15) is sufficient to have coverage of most of the edges, again highlighting that we can reduce this parameter without losing coverage in this graph model. However, unlike the uniform results, we see a less extreme dropoff with a size of 8 still having over 80% of the edges in comparison to the uniform case having around 20% highlighting the difference that the sampling strategy makes, as sampling random walks by definition includes at least some edges, unlike the uniform sampling.

2 Discussion of the sampling methods

In this section, we present an extended discussion regarding the number of subgraphs needed to build the data sets based on the number of nodes and sampling method.

Random Walk: Suppose one was to sample a single long random walk, then Theorem 2.1 in [6] gives that the time it takes for the random walk to cover the whole graph of n vertices with high probability (henceforth the *cover time*) is bounded below by $(1 - o(1)) \log n$ and bounded above by $(\frac{4}{27} + o(1)) n^3$. [5] This bound is tight, see [5]; the *lollipop graph* (a path of length $n/3$ connected to a clique on $2n/3$ nodes) achieves the maximum. Thus, a single long walk of length $T \approx \frac{4}{27} n^3$ has a high probability of covering all vertices, and its induced subgraph would then cover the whole graph.

The SAGESSE sampling method is slightly different; however one could glue $\lfloor T/k \rfloor$ walks of length k together at their endpoint to obtain one long path of length T . Thus, when sampling of order $\frac{4}{27k} n^3$ random walks, there is a good chance that the whole graph can be recovered from its induced subgraphs. However, this upper bound can be quite coarse; [3] shows that for sparse Bernoulli random graphs with edge probability $p = c \frac{\log n}{n}$ (with $c > 1$ so that the graph is connected with high probability), the cover time behaves asymptotically as $c \log \left(\frac{c}{c-1} \right) n \log n$, with high probability.

Moreover, [1] shows that when running $d = O(\log n)$ random walks in parallel starting from the same node, which is the regime used in SAGESSE, then in many graphs there is a speed-up of the cover time which is linear in d ; [4] extend this result to d to be of the same order as n . Thus, it is not unrealistic to assume that for an unknown graph, after order $n^2 \log(n)$ steps of the walk, all nodes in the network are covered with high probability. If one long walk covers all nodes of the graph, then the subgraph induced by its nodes coincides with the graph.

Figure 2: Ablation on the random walk sampling model. Percentage of edges of the original graph that are part of any of the sampled subgraphs as a function of the number of subgraph samples in the random walk sampling model. **Top panel:** varies the random walk length with the subgraphs per node fixed at 10. **Bottom panel:** varies the number of subgraphs sampled per node, with the number of random walks fixed at 30.

In the SAGESSE construction though, induced subgraphs are only taken for walks of length k . Hence there may be some edges left unexplored for some time longer than the walks take to cover all edges. In a related problem, [2] shows that if one keeps track of the number of edges which the random walk traverses, the time until the random walk has covered all edges can be much larger than the time for it to cover all nodes. This is a crude bound as, in fact, we simply need each node from an edge to exist in the same short walk, due to the induced nature of sampling. In the absence of theoretical results to draw on, it is a heuristic assumption that in our setting, when many nodes will be covered more than once, the subgraphs induced by the small walks will cover the whole network with high probability.

2-hop modified neighborhood: For snowball sampling without neighborhood size restriction, taking n samples, by sampling the 2-hop neighborhood of every node, obviously suffices to cover the whole network.

When the size of the subgraph is fixed to k , then the problem becomes more challenging as we need to remove a certain number of nodes from the neighborhood to satisfy this requirement. We could think of such a reduced sample of a 2-hop neighborhood as containing a random walk of size 2. Then the same arguments as for random

walk sampling apply to conclude that if $d = \Theta(\log n)$ subgraphs are generated per node, is not unrealistic to assume that for an unknown graph, after order $n^2 \log(n)$ steps of the 2-hop walks, with high probability all nodes in the network are covered.

Method	EuCore	Cora	Wiki	Facebook	SBM
SAGESS-Unif	41.11	-	-	38.81	9.29
SAGESS-RW	47.01	73.29	60.63	43.95	10.57
SAGESS-Ego	48.21	88.50	53.43	40.00	9.18
NetGAN	30.61	0.45	2.57	41.20	9.81
EDGE	8.60	0.07	0.34	2.17	2.77
CELL	32.11	50.13	33.43	32.56	11.26
DCSBM	3.71	0.15	0.28	2.94	4.12

Table 2: Percentage of edge overlap between synthetic dataset and training dataset.

Edge overlap Table 2 shows the overlap of edges in different data sets and different methods. This aims at showing how our model is able to retrieve the initial edges by checking the percentage of edges generated by SAGESS actually present in the training graph. There does not seem to be a strong connection between density and edge overlap.

3 Hyperparameters

Here we detail the experimental setups of our simulations. First we establish notation; namely, e denotes the number of epochs, k is the size of the subgraphs in the training data set, and d is the number of subgraphs generated per node. The parameters of DIGRESS were set to the same values for all the experiments in the main paper: number of epochs $e = 200$, and the number of diffusion steps $T = 500$. For the number of subgraphs, we performed the experiments in the main paper with subgraphs of size $k = 15$ for Cora and Wiki, $k = 30$ for Facebook and the SBM, and $k = 50$ for EuCore. Moreover, the rule of thumb for setting the parameter d was to set it to 10 if the number of nodes in the initial graph was below 2000, and 20 on a data set with more than 2000 nodes. For the benchmark models, we used the default parameters in the respective libraries for NetGAN, CELL, and SBM, as we did not perform almost any hyperparameter optimization on DIGRESS and used the default setup in the original code.

4 Computational Resources

To perform our experiments on the benchmark methods, we had access to an NVIDIA Tesla V100 with 32GB of RAM and Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5 – 2698 v4 at 2.20GHz.

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